

On Specially Multiplicative Functions

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ABSTRACT:

An arithmetic function q is specially multiplicative if it is the Dirichlet product of two completely multiplicative functions, thus for a fixed prime number p , we know that the sequence $\{q(p^n)\}$ satisfies an interesting recurrence relation which here we study for several arithmetic functions.

Keywords: Sum of divisors function, Recurrence relations, Ramanujan's tau function, Z-transform, Divisor function, Specially multiplicative function, Sequences of integers, Sum of squares, Alternating sum of divisors function.

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INTRODUCTION

If the arithmetic function q is specially multiplicative then it verifies the following recurrence relation [1]:

$$q(p^{n+2}) = q(p) q(p^{n+1}) + (q(p^2) - (q(p))^2) q(p^n), \quad n \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

where p is an arbitrary prime number. If we introduce the sequence $\{f_n\} = \{q(p^n)\}$, then (1) acquires the form:

$$f_{n+2} = f_1 f_{n+1} + (f_2 - (f_1)^2) f_n, \quad (2)$$

which can be studied via Z-transform [2]. In Sec. 2 we analyze (1) and (2) for several specially multiplicative functions.

DIRICHLET PRODUCT OF TWO COMPLETELY MULTIPLICATIVE FUNCTIONS

a). Alternating sum of divisors function [3]. This arithmetic function β is the Dirichlet product between the identity and Liouville completely multiplicative functions [4], in fact, $\beta = I \cdot \lambda$, therefore:

$$\beta(n) = \sum_{d|n} \lambda(d) \frac{n}{d} = \sum_{d|n} (-1)^{\Omega(d)} \frac{n}{d}, \beta(1) = 1, \beta(p) = p - 1, \beta(p^2) = p^2 - p + 1, \quad (3)$$

where $\Omega(m)$ is the total number of prime factors of m , each being counted according to its multiplicity. In this case the recurrence (2) gives the expression:

$$f_{n+2} = (p - 1)f_{n+1} + p f_n, \quad n \geq 0, \quad (4)$$

and its Z-transform [2] has the structure $F(z) = \frac{z}{z-p} \cdot \frac{z}{z+1}$, hence $\{f_n\}$ is the Cauchy convolution [4] of the sequences $\{p^n\}$ and $\{(-1)^n\}$:

$$f_n = (-1)^n \sum_{j=0}^n (-p)^j = (-1)^n \frac{1 - (-p)^{n+1}}{1 - (-p)} \quad \therefore \quad \beta(p^n) = \frac{(-1)^n + p^{n+1}}{1 + p}, \quad (5)$$

in agreement with [3]. For example, any integer can be written in the form $n = 2^k m$, $k \geq 0$, with m odd, then from (5):

$$\beta(n) = \beta(2^k) \beta(m) = \frac{1}{3} ((-1)^k + 2^{k+1}) \beta(m). \quad (6)$$

b). Sum of divisors functions [1, 4-6]. The functions $\sigma_k = I_k \cdot e$ are specially multiplicative with $e(m) = 1$ and $I_k(m) = m^k$, that is:

$$\sigma_k(n) = \sum_{d|n} d^k \quad \therefore \quad \sigma_k(1) = 1, \quad \sigma_k(p) = p^k + 1, \quad \sigma_k(p^2) = p^{2k} + p^k + 1, \quad (7)$$

then (2) generates the following recurrence relation:

$$f_{n+2} = (1 + p^k)f_{n+1} - p^k f_n, \quad n \geq 0, \quad (8)$$

and its Z-transform gives the relation $F(z) = \frac{z}{z-1} \cdot \frac{z}{z-p^k}$, therefore $\{f_n\}$ is the Cauchy product between $\{1^n\}$ and $\{(p^k)^n\}$:

$$f_n = \sum_{j=0}^n (p^k)^j \quad \therefore \quad \sigma_k(p^n) = \frac{1 - p^{k(n+1)}}{1 - p^k}, \quad (9)$$

in total harmony with [6]. In particular $\sigma_0 = d$ is the ordinary divisor function, that is, $d(n) = \sum_{d|n} 1$ is the number of divisors of n , thus in this case from (8) and (9) the recurrence $d(p^{n+2}) = 2 d(p^{n+1}) - d(p^n)$ is verified because $d(p^m) = m + 1$.

c). Sums of two squares [7-11]. The arithmetic function $r_2(m)$ is the number of representations of m as a sum of two squares, and $\frac{1}{4}r_2$ is specially multiplicative via the Jacobi expression [1, 4, 12, 13]:

$$\frac{1}{4}r_2 = \chi_4 \cdot e \quad \therefore \quad \frac{1}{4}r_2(n) = \sum_{d|n} \chi_4(d), \quad (10)$$

where the completely multiplicative function χ_4 is the non-trivial Dirichlet character (mod 4) [4, 7, 14, 15]:

$$\chi_4(m) = \begin{cases} 1, & m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, \\ -1, & m \equiv -1 \pmod{4}, \\ 0, & m \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \end{cases} = \begin{cases} (-1)^{\frac{m-1}{2}}, & m \text{ is odd}, \\ 0, & m \text{ is even}, \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

then (10) satisfies the recurrence relation (2):

$$4r_2(p^{n+2}) = r_2(p)r_2(p^{n+1}) + \left(r_2(p^2) - \frac{1}{4}(r_2(p))^2\right)r_2(p^n), \quad n \geq 0, \quad (12)$$

which can be verified using the result [8]:

$$r_2(p^n) = \begin{cases} 4, & p = 2 \text{ or } p \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \text{ and } n \text{ even}, \\ 4(n+1), & p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}, \\ 3, & p \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \text{ and } n \text{ odd}, \end{cases} \quad n \geq 0. \quad (13)$$

d). *Ramanujan's tau function* [16-18]. This arithmetic function is not specially multiplicative, however, $\tau(p^n)$ satisfies (2) [4, 16, 17, 19-23]:

$$\tau(p^{n+2}) = \tau(p)\tau(p^{n+1}) - p^{11}\tau(p^n), \quad n \geq 0, \quad \tau(1) = 1, \quad \tau(p^2) = (\tau(p))^2 - p^{11}, \quad (14)$$

and the corresponding Z-transform is given by:

$$F(z) = \frac{z}{z-a} \cdot \frac{z}{z-\underline{a}}, \quad a = \frac{\tau(p)}{2} - iA, \quad A^2 = p^{11} - \frac{(\tau(p))^2}{4} \geq 0, \quad (15)$$

hence $\{f_n\}$ is the Cauchy convolution of the sequences $\{a^n\}$ and $\{\underline{a}^n\}$:

$$f_n = \underline{a}^n \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{a^2}{p^{11}}^j \quad \therefore \quad \tau(p^n) = \frac{1}{2}(a^n + \underline{a}^n) + i \frac{\tau(p)}{4A}(a^n - \underline{a}^n), \quad (16)$$

which can be simplified to obtain the following Gandhi's expression [4, 24]:

$$\tau(p^n) = \sum_{j=0}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor} (-1)^j (n-j) \binom{n-2j}{p^{11}}^j (\tau(p))^{n-2j}. \quad (17)$$

If we introduce θ_p such that $\sin \theta_p = \frac{A}{p^{11/2}}$ and $\cos \theta_p = \frac{\tau(p)}{2p^{11/2}}$, then $a = p^{11/2}e^{-i\theta_p}$ and (16) takes the form published by Ramanujan [16]:

$$\tau(p^n) = \frac{\sin(n+1)\theta_p}{\sin \theta_p} p^{11n/2}. \quad (18)$$

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